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Pedro Rodrigues is a Phd in Environmental Contamination and Toxicology and researcher at CIIMAR. His research focuses on the embryotoxicity and -omics alterations caused by emerging contaminants and their metabolites in aquatic and soil vertebrate and invertebrate species. The main goals of his work are to provide useful knowledge and tools to assess the potential impacts of emerging contaminants on non-target species, and consequently improve the existing monitoring programmes and establish safe limits for these compounds in the environment.

FENPYROXIMATE AFFINITY TO THE NADH-UBIQUINONE OXIDOREDUCTASE PROTEIN FROM COMPLEX I FOR 26 DIFFERENT BEE SPECIES

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Abstract

Pesticide usage has a valuable impact on agriculture. However, it also has detrimental environmental impacts on soil, water, and non-target species, potentially leading to a decrease in biodiversity. The decline of bee populations due to pesticide use is one of the most recognised examples. Fenpyroximate (FEN) is a fungicide that inhibits mitochondrial complex I electron transport, focusing on the translocation of protons from NADH to ubiquinone oxidoreductase. Moreover, it was already detected in Caatinga crops and was reported to negatively impact bees [1;2]. Therefore, the main aim of this work is to evaluate the sensibility of different species of bees from the Caatinga biome to FEN, employing an *in silico* approach. A protein-ligand analysis was used to determine FEN's affinity and binding sites to the NADH-ubiquinone oxidoreductase complex I protein (NADH)

for 26 different bee species inhabiting the Caatinga biome. A phylogenetic tree was performed to determine the similarity and position of similar binding sites and pockets, and the protein-ligand docking was performed with Autodock (v4.2.6). Results showed that NADH sequences for the 26 bee species ranged between 438 and 566 bp, sharing 79% of pairwise residues. Also, the binding energy of FEN to NADH was found to have values between - 8.39 and -10.28kcal/mol, the ligand efficiency was between 0.27 and 0.32, and inhibition constants were between 28.98 and 713 nM. A minimum of 3 and a maximum of 10 ligand aminoacids were found for the 26 evaluated species. This bioinformatics analysis methodology proved to be a useful complementary tool to animal testing, providing valuable insights for determining the mechanisms underlying the toxicity of pesticides in bee species. Additionally, it allowed us to determine a rank of species sensitivity to FEN that can be used as a baseline for future conservation policies.

References

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